

Supplementary material to: “Seasonal synchronization of sleep timing in industrial and pre-industrial societies”

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ABSTRACT

Figure S1. Locations of the societies whose sleep timing is analyzed in this manuscript on an azimuthal projection centered at $\lambda_0 = 18^\circ 8'$ west of UTC prime meridian and 52° latitude. The picture shows the Earth on a unique hemisphere from Equator (bottom) to the Pole (top). Solid symbols display societies with access to electricity. Open symbols display societies without access to electricity. Crosses display pairs of pre-industrial societies with and without access to electricity. Rounded symbols refer to societies physically in the Northern Hemisphere. Rest of symbols locate societies physically in the Southern Hemisphere. Circles of latitude in heavy dash-dotted lines are the Equator, the Tropic (at $\phi = \varepsilon$) and the Polar Circle (at $\phi = 90^\circ - \varepsilon$). Circles of latitude in light dashed lines run values of the shortest photoperiod D_w , increasing in steps of 1 h; the circle nearest to the Polar Circle is $D_w = 5$ h. The picture separates light and dark in the winter day at noon over the meridian λ_0 . Continental and lake polygons were taken from <http://www.naturalearthdata.com/>.